

Orchids of Romania Part 2

Nora de Angelli continues her account of orchids found in different regions of Romania (photos by Nora de Angelli)

Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve

Southeast Romania, neighbouring the Dobrogea Plateau, is the site of a natural wonder – the Danube delta. Considered the most beautiful and biodiverse delta in Europe, this Biosphere Reserve was declared a UNESCO World Heritage Site in 1991. The delta is renowned as one of the greatest wetlands on earth, harbouring an impressive number of aquatic and terrestrial species of fauna and flora, some unique. This coastal wildlife paradise, which consists of 23 natural ecosystems, is formed within the Danube River's immense estuary, just before the river flows into the

Epipactis danubialis in Letea Forest Protected Area within the Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve

Black Sea. It forms an intricate labyrinth of alluvial plains, marshes, rivers, canals, streamlets, reed islands and lakes. The richness of nutrients found in the mixing of freshwater and seawater and in the sediments brought by the river, make this hydrological basin one of the most biodiverse natural habitats in the world.

Letea Forest Protected Area

Hidden in the heart of the delta is the mysterious Letea Forest, the oldest natural reserve in Romania, dating back to 1938. Getting there involves several hours' boat travel on the canals, followed by a car safari, all under the watchful eye of a specialised guide. This lush forest grows entirely on alluvial sand dunes and closely resembles a tropical jungle, with wild lianas and silk vines (*Periploca graeca*) entwined like enormous tentacles around the branches of ancient trees.

This magic place hides two of the most interesting orchids, *Epipactis danubialis* and *Epacts. guegelii*, the latter endemic to Romania.

Epipactis danubialis was discovered in 1986 by the Czech botanist Jaroslav Rydlo, during an expedition to the Letea Forest. In 1988, Karl Robatsch (1929–2000), a well-known Austrian chess player and botanist, visited Letea Forest and, in 1989, described this very rare species as *Epipactis danubialis* Robatsch & Rydlo. It is now considered to be a form of *Epacts. atrorubens*

The discovery of *Epacts. danubialis* is reminiscent of tales of 19th century orchid hunters in the jungles of South America and Asia. It occurred before 1989, during the dark communist times in Romania. In 1986, following a cultural-scientific collaboration between Romania and the former Czechoslovakia, a group of ornithologists was invited to carry out a scientific expedition in the Letea Forest. Among them was Jaroslav Rydlo, a specialist in European orchids, who had a keen and practiced eye for *Epipactis*. He found a group

Epipactis guegelii in Letea Forest Protected Area

of these plants but could not identify them precisely because the flowers had withered. However, he realised that they were different from other known species of *Epipactis* and, two years later, Karl Robatsch, impressed by Rydlo's descriptions, decided to search for these plants in Letea Forest on his own. Knowing the exact location, he found a few individuals and photographed them for later study. But just before leaving the reserve, he was caught by the local communist police (Securitate) and his camera and films were immediately confiscated. Robatsch was detained and accused of espionage while his films were developed. To the disappointment of the Securitate, the films contained only a few insignificant images of wild plants. No longer suspected of being a spy, Robatsch

was released, but expelled from the country. In the following year, he published a detailed description of the small plants, which he called *Epipactis danubialis* Robatsch & Rydl (Linzer *Biologische Beiträge*, 21 (1-2): 296 (1989)).

Seven years later, in July 1995, Robatsch discovered the Romanian endemic *Epipactis guegelii*, growing along with *Epipactis danubialis* in remote areas of the Letea Forest. He published a full description in 1997 in the *Journal Europäischer Orchideen* (J. Eur. Orch. 28 (4): 767 (1997)).

Transylvania – The Land of Vampires

I cannot end my story without talking about one of the most beautiful regions of Romania – one of myths, legends and

... vampires. With a typical continental climate, Transylvania, the land “beyond the forest”, is a true orchid paradise. From the beautiful and picturesque hills of Maramures and the Apuseni Mountains to the Terra Siculorum, dozens of rare orchid species may be encountered, between early March (*Anacamptis morio*) and late November (*Spiranthes spiralis*).

The most spectacular of all is the imposing, 1m tall, *Ant. palustris* subsp. *elegans*, in a wide range of colours, from deep purple to pink and even white.

The other end of the spectrum is represented by three tiny, inconspicuous and extremely rare species, in Romania

A grasshopper (*Chorthippus dorsatus*) rests peacefully on *Spiranthes spiralis*

Malaxis monophyllus in shady, mixed forest; beside it is the empty, sun-bleached shell of an edible snail

Anacamptis palustris subsp. *elegans* var. *albiflora*. Harghita County, Transylvania. The inflorescence is visited by a common cockchafer (maybug), *Melolontha melolontha*

Herminium monorchis, the musk orchid

occurring only in Transylvania. *Malaxis monophyllos*, which flowers in July, is found in Bicaz Gorge, and *Herminium monorchis* and *Liparis loeselii*, flowering in June to July, occur in small populations of only 2–8 individuals in the wet meadows and swampy areas of Brasov county.

One of the most abundant and beautiful species in Transylvania is the chromatically versatile *Dactylorhiza sambucina*. It presents two very distinct colour morphs, yellow and red, with an intermediate salmon-pink one. These contrasting chromatic variations deceive pollinators, which after learning to avoid the nectarless yellow flowers, land on their red or peach-coloured neighbours, ultimately accomplishing the pollination of the species.

Liparis loeselii growing in a shady sphagnum bog alongside the sundew *Drosera anglica* and the butterwort *Pinguicula vulgaris*, both insectivorous

Dactylorhiza sambucina – yellow variety. A common blue butterfly, *Polyommatus icarus*, is resting/sleeping on the inflorescence at dusk. Harghita County

Dactylorhiza traunsteineri subsp. *schurii* in Brasov county

A colony of *Dactylorhiza sambucina* in Harghita county, including two of the colour variants

Gymnadenia frivaldii in Harghita Mădăraș Protected Area

Transylvania is also home to a few endemic *Dactylorhiza* subspecies such as *Dact. traunsteineri* subsp. *schurii*, flowering in Brasov county between June and July, and *Dact. cordigera* subsp. *sicolorum* (now subsp. *cordigera*) and its rare *albiflora* form, found in Terra Sicularum, a region that covers Covasna, Harghita and Mureș counties. *Dactylorhiza maculata* subsp. *transsilvanica* (now subsp. *maculata*), first discovered in Transylvania by the Hungarian botanist Károly Rezső Soó von Bere (1903–1980), is another important representative of the local flora.

Deep within the remote, wild swamps of the Harghita Mădăraș protected area, *Gymnadenia frivaldii*, a vulnerable orchid of particular beauty, is found.

Dactylorhiza cordigera subsp. *sicolorum* in Harghita Mădăraș Protected Area

Cephalanthera longifolia in Transylvania

Cephalanthera rubra, *Ceph. longifolia* and *Ceph. damasonium* occur in large populations within the ancient Transylvanian forests. *Epipactis* is also widely represented in Transylvania, including the rare *Epcts. albensis* and *Epcts. purpurata* f. *rosea*.

A natural hybrid new to science

Probably the most interesting of all Transylvanian orchids is *x Pseudorhiza nieschalkii* nothosubsp. *sicolorum*, an intergeneric hybrid discovered for the first time by the biologist Hajnalka Kertész on 30 June 2020, during a field trip to Terra Sicularum.

While researching the orchid species of the Harghita Mădăraș heathlands, Hajnalka

Cephalanthera damasonium in Transylvania

Cephalanthera rubra in Transylvania

A pink form of the violet helleborine, *Epipactis purpurata*, in Transylvania

spotted an odd-looking plant which, from a distance, resembled *Pseudorchis. albida* subsp. *tricuspis*. After parting the dense grass that surrounded the plant, she realised it was something more than just *Pse. albida* subsp. *tricuspis*. She sent me several mobile phone photos, which took me completely by surprise! I realised that the plant was a miracle of nature – an unexpected cross between two subspecies in different genera, *Dactylorhiza fuchsii* subsp. *sooana* and *Pseudorchis albida* subsp. *tricuspis*. Following

detailed morphological and genetic analyses, we concluded that she had discovered a unique combination, an intergeneric hybrid that proved to be new to science.

In years to come, I hope that our orchid research will continue and new discoveries will be made in this region of breath-taking scenery and rich history. It is not surprising that HRH the Prince of Wales fell in love with this magical place and decided to call it his “second home”, investing a lot of time and effort into promoting Transylvania to the world.

x *Pseudorhiza nieschalkii* nothosubsp. *siculorum* in Harghita Mădăraş Protected Area

Pseudorchis albida subsp. *tricuspis* in Harghita Mădăraş Protected Area